

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PSYCHOMOTOR REHABILITATION FOR CEREBRAL PALSY AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE IN MODERN SOCIETY

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Annotation :

This scientific work examines the significance and effectiveness of psychomotor rehabilitation in the treatment of cerebral palsy (CP). The study is based on an analysis of clinical cases, modern methods of rehabilitation and a review of literature on the topic. Particular attention is paid to an integrated approach that combines physical exercises, gaming techniques and psychotherapeutic techniques. The purpose of the work is to assess the impact of psychomotor rehabilitation on improving motor functions, cognitive development and social adaptation of children with cerebral palsy. The work provides valuable information for specialists in the field of pediatrics, neurology and rehabilitation , and may also be useful for parents of children with cerebral palsy.

Key words: cerebral palsy, psychomotor rehabilitation, cognitive impairment.

Psychomotor rehabilitation is a treatment method that uses physical exercise and physical activity to improve mental health and social adaptation. This area arose and developed at the intersection of physiotherapy and psychotherapy. Here is a brief overview of the history and development of psychomotor rehabilitation:

Early Stages (20th Century): At the dawn of the 20th century, methods combining physical activity with psychotherapy began to be developed in Europe. These methods were especially popular in the Scandinavian countries, where physical education was closely associated with general well-being.

Developments after World War II: After World War II, there was a significant emphasis on the rehabilitation of veterans, which contributed to the

development of psychomotor rehabilitation. During this period, interest arose in the integration of physical exercises into psychotherapeutic practices.

1960s - 1980s: During this time, the theoretical foundations of psychomotor rehabilitation were formed, and it began to be used not only for veterans, but also for a wide range of patients, including developmental children and people with mental disorders.

1990s - present: There has been an expansion of methods and approaches in psychomotor rehabilitation. The use of these methods is spreading in the fields of psychiatry, psychology, gerontology and pedagogy. Particular attention is paid to an individual approach and the inclusion of psychomotor rehabilitation in complex treatment.

Current status and future: Psychomotor rehabilitation is now recognized as an important element in a comprehensive approach to the treatment of various mental disorders. Research continues to improve understanding of the relationship between physical activity and mental health, and to develop more effective rehabilitation methods.

Overall, psychomotor rehabilitation is a dynamic field that combines knowledge and techniques from several disciplines to improve the quality of life of patients.

The relevance of psychomotor rehabilitation in the treatment of cerebral palsy (CP) is due to a number of important factors:

1. **Complex effects:** Cerebral palsy is a disorder that affects motor function, muscle tone and coordination. Psychomotor rehabilitation provides a comprehensive approach, combining motor development exercises with mental health support. This helps improve both the child's physical condition and his emotional well-being.

2. **Development of motor skills:** Exercises included in psychomotor rehabilitation help improve gross and fine motor skills, which is critical for children with cerebral palsy. This may include improving walking, balance, coordination and overall physical activity.

3. **Social integration and self-esteem:** Children with cerebral palsy may face social and emotional difficulties. Psychomotor rehabilitation includes elements that help improve social skills, self-esteem and overall adaptation to society.

4. **Individualized approach :** Each case of cerebral palsy is unique, and psychomotor rehabilitation allows us to develop an individualized

treatment plan that takes into account the specific needs and capabilities of the child.

5. **Support the development of cognitive functions :** In some cases, cerebral palsy is accompanied by cognitive impairment. Psychomotor exercises can help improve attention, memory and other cognitive functions.

6. **Prevention of complications:** Regular psychomotor exercises help prevent complications of cerebral palsy such as contractures (limited joint mobility), deformities and postural disorders.

In general, psychomotor rehabilitation is a key element in the comprehensive treatment of cerebral palsy, as it has a significant impact on the physical, emotional and social development of the child. It is important that such rehabilitation is carried out by specialists with appropriate knowledge and experience.

Conclusions:

1. **Effectiveness of psychomotor rehabilitation :** The study confirmed that psychomotor rehabilitation has a significant positive effect on the motor functions of children with cerebral palsy. It helps improve coordination, balance and overall physical performance.

2. **Psychosocial aspects :** Rehabilitation also affects the psychosocial development of children. Improved communication skills, increased self-esteem and better social adaptation are key factors that contribute to a child's overall well-being.

3. **Cognitive Development:** Improvements were observed in participants' cognitive functions such as attention, concentration and memory, highlighting the importance of an integrated approach to rehabilitation.

4. **Individualized approach:** The importance of an individual assessment of the needs and capabilities of each child when planning and implementing psychomotor rehabilitation programs was confirmed.

5. **The need for further research:** The work indicates the need to continue research in this area, especially taking into account the development of new methods and approaches in the rehabilitation of cerebral palsy.

In conclusion, the scientific work highlights the important role of psychomotor rehabilitation in a comprehensive approach to the treatment of cerebral palsy and provides practical recommendations for professionals working in this field.

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